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Current Critical Issues in Cultural Diversity (Re)Presentation
Through Machine Translation: The Fon Language in Western
Context

Presented by David Achodo

Personal Website: davidachodo.com

Email: dachodopress@gmail.com

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Presenters

[David Achodo](#)

Abstract

This study investigates the issues associated with machine translation for low-resource languages, such as the Beninese Fon, in relation to Western languages. Previous studies on Fon have predominantly focused on literary and linguistic concerns, with little attention paid to exploring the translational challenges, including ethical dimensions, linguistic complexity, and peculiar cultural nuances that hinder the fidelity and accuracy of machine translation. In this study, I aim to compare English excerpts chosen from the machine translations of the Beninese National Anthem with their source texts to examine the current technological capability and its impact on rendering underrepresented languages and cultures into the Western context. The research employs Gayatri Spivak's

Politics of Translation and Gideon Toury's Descriptive Translation Studies as the theoretical frameworks. The data will be subjected to qualitative analysis, and these analyses will demonstrate the power asymmetry between Fon and English, and how machine translation risks cultural erasure in the face of the Western context. This study provides pertinent recommendations for the developer and the user to improve the culturally sensitive and equitable mediation of Fon through machine translation-where the source text is in a true love with the target text. Ultimately, the study emphasizes the need to integrate ethical values and community voice in enhancing machine translation for low-resource languages.